

ADVANCEMENTS IN TECHNOLOGIES FOR AIR POLLUTION MITIGATION

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Abstract. Air pollution from volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) presents a complex environmental challenge shaped by multiple pollutants. Despite concerted efforts in the last twenty years, air quality continues to pose serious risks to both human health and environmental stability. Exposure to VOCs and PM_{2.5} indoors can lead to significant health issues, including respiratory illnesses, leukemia, birth defects, and miscarriages. Therefore, advancing indoor air purification technologies is essential to reduce these harmful effects. This article examines the latest trends, innovations, and potential future developments in indoor air purification methods.

Keywords: VOCs, PM_{2.5}, adsorption, metal-organic frameworks, photocatalytic oxidation, catalysts, additives

Introduction. Air pollution due to CO₂ emissions and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is a multifaceted ecological challenge influenced by various pollutants. Particulate matter, categorized as PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}, poses serious health risks associated with air pollution. Short-term exposure to elevated levels can worsen asthma and other respiratory conditions, impair lung function, and even lead to premature mortality. These particles can result from both direct emissions and the atmospheric transformation of precursor gases like NO_x, sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and ammonia, which also have detrimental effects on plants and human health.

Adsorbent Materials Traditional adsorbent materials vary in composition and effectiveness for adsorbing pollutants from industrial emissions, largely influenced by their chemical properties and the concentration of pollutants. Activated carbon is recognized as one of the most effective adsorbents, though it can be relatively expensive [1]. Zeolite molecular sieves,

another significant adsorbent, are inorganic crystalline materials characterized by a regular porous structure, strong acidity, and high hydrothermal stability, making them valuable in environmental remediation [2]. Biochar-based adsorption of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) operates through unique mechanisms, including adsorption in the carbonized phase and partitioning in the non-carbonized organic matter [3]. Biochars from different feedstocks show considerable variations in surface area, morphology, and elemental ratios like H/C and O/C, even under similar pyrolysis conditions. For instance, biochar derived from bamboo may achieve a specific surface area of 375 m²/g at 600 °C, while biochar from switchgrass might only reach 15 m²/g [4].

Table 1 presents data on 15 different types of biocoals used for VOC gas adsorption. Among these, acetone has the highest adsorption capacity at 483.09 mg/g, while benzene and toluene have capacities of 161.42 mg/g and 424.4 mg/g, respectively [5].

Table 1.

Sorption Capacities of Various Biocoals for VOC Gases.

Adsorbate	Formula	Weight	Adsorption capacity	Source
Acetone	C3H6O	58.08	483.09	[3]
Acetone	C3H6O	58.08	343.89	[3]
Benzene	C6H6	78.11	27.5	[4]
Benzene	C6H6	78.11	161.42	[5]
Butanol	C4H9OH	74.12	262.38	[6]
Cyclohexane	C6H12	84.16	327.18	[6]
Ethyl acetate	C4H8O2	88.11	420.92	[7]
Ethyl acetate	C4H8O2	88.11	450.24	[5]
Isopropyl acetate	C5H10O2	102.13	147.45	[7]
Isopropyl acetate	C5H10O2	116.16	151.71	[7]
Toluene	C7H8	92.14	366.72	[4]
Toluene	C7H8	92.14	424.4	[3]

Methanol has the lowest adsorption capacity among VOC gases, measuring just 10.6 mg/g. The adsorption rate is mainly determined by the surface area of the biochar and its non-carbonized organic components. Increasing the temperature during biomass processing does not notably enhance VOC removal efficiency

with biochar. Due to its cost-effectiveness and widespread availability, biochar serves as a practical adsorbent for VOCs. Additionally, incorporating nanoparticles with activated carbon improves the effectiveness of formaldehyde removal from the gas emission [6].

Reducing emissions through Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs).

Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are a new class of crystalline materials that leverage the advantages of both organic and inorganic components. These materials are composed of metal ions or clusters interconnected by organic linkers [7]. MOFs are characterized by their large surface areas, varied functionalities, and remarkable thermal stability, making them highly suitable for various applications, including gas storage, separation technologies, pollutant capture, and chemical degradation processes.

To achieve uniform particle sizes in Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), parameters such as electric field strength and the flow rate of the polymer solution during electrospinning can be optimized. This method facilitates the development of composite polymer filters using PAN, PS, and PVP, capitalizing on the high adsorption capacity of MOFs while ensuring the filters remain flexible. By adjusting mat diameters, PAN concentration (ranging from 6% to 10% by weight), and MOF content (between 20% and 60% by weight), particle sizes can be controlled to fall between 200 nm and 1 μm [7].

Through fuel additives. PM_{2.5} emissions primarily stem from vehicles, and improving the performance of exhaust systems can be achieved by adding various additives to promote complete combustion and meet technical standards. Internal combustion engines release fine particulate matter (PM) into the atmosphere during fossil fuel combustion, which poses significant risks to human health and the environment. These aerosols can be identified by their content of naturally occurring inorganic elements (such as K, Na, Cl, S, Ca, Mg, Si, P, Zn, Pb) or organic compounds (like C, H, O). Organic emissions, including PAHs, VOCs, and tar, primarily arise from the complete oxidation of exhaust gases. Recent studies have noted advancements in diesel particulate filter (DPF) technologies, which include new substrate materials, innovative catalyst formulations, improved regeneration techniques, unmonitored DPF regenerations, and enhanced management strategies [8]. Future compliance with strict emission regulations is anticipated to involve closed-loop regeneration systems and highly efficient gasoline particulate filters (GPF) [9].

The table below summarizes general information regarding the composition of diesel exhaust additives [10].

Table 2.
Diesel fuel additives *

Additive group	Content
Diesel fuel stabilizers	Antioxidants (linked phenol, phenylenediamines), dispersants (without ash succinimides , polymer methacrylates), metal deactivators (N,N'-disalicylidene-1,2-propanediamine)
Additives that increase cetane number	Alkyl nitrates , 2 ethylhexyl nitrate
Multifunctional diesel additive packages	Wax crystalline modifiers and flow enhancers , deodorants , package stability for from the solvent except of the above combination
Fuel catalyts	Cerium (Ce), iron compounds , platinum
Catalysts	Platinum group elements

* The table is compiled based on the data: ATC Fuel additives and the environment, 2004.

Diesel Fuel Stabilizers. Diesel fuel instability can result in resin formation, which may clog fuel injectors or filters. Several types of diesel fuel instability exist, and various additives are used to mitigate these issues:

1. **Stabilizers** - These additives serve to neutralize acidic substances, thereby preventing acid-base reactions and resulting in soluble products that remain stable and do not participate in further reactions. Stabilizers are usually formulated with strong basic amines and are utilized in concentrations between 50 and 200 mg/kg [10].
2. **Antioxidants** - These substances are employed to prevent reactions that contribute to soot formation. Common antioxidants include phenols and specific amines such as phenylenediamine, which are typically added at concentrations ranging from 10 to 80 mg/kg [10].
3. **Dispersants** - These agents are designed to prevent the clumping of soot particles and their subsequent deposition by inhibiting adhesion and

accumulation. Dispersants like succinimides or polymer methacrylates are typically utilized at concentrations between 15 and 100 mg/kg [10].

4. **Metal Deactivators** - These additives serve to neutralize trace metals that might act as catalysts in instability reactions. One such example is N,N'-disalicylidene-1,2-propanediamine, which is typically used at concentrations ranging from 1 to 15 mg/kg [10].
5. **Detergents** - Detergents are crucial for ensuring optimal injector performance in diesel engines. They create a protective layer on metal surfaces and inhibit deposit formation in injector nozzles through emulsification. Commonly used detergents include succinimides and other ashless polymeric compounds, which are added at concentrations between 10 and 200 mg/kg [10].

Multifunctional Diesel Additive Packages. These additive packages may consist of various components, such as detergents, cetane enhancers, stabilizers, lubricity agents, antifoaming agents, deodorants, demulsifiers, corrosion inhibitors, and antioxidants. These substances are typically added at concentrations between 100 and 1500 mg/kg [10].

In a separate study, acrylic terpolymers containing different alkyl radicals were synthesized to determine which radicals in poly(alkyl acrylate) (PAA) samples would produce the highest viscosity index at lower polymer concentrations [11]. Furthermore, the effects of these additives on the low temperature performance, electrical conductivity, and wear resistance of GTL (Gas to Liquid) diesel were evaluated [11].

A synergistic effect was noted when the terpolymers were combined with Keroflux 6100, a pour point depressant, in GTL diesel. The addition of 0.1% w/w of the terpolymers led to a substantial increase in the electrical conductivity of the GTL diesel [11].

Challenges and Future Directions. The review article outlines significant progress in air purification technologies, while also identifying ongoing challenges. Traditional adsorbents like activated carbon and biochar have demonstrated potential, but issues with scalability, cost, and long-term effectiveness persist. Future efforts should concentrate on enhancing these materials through innovative modifications and the integration of nanomaterials to boost adsorption capacity and regeneration efficiency. Additionally, it's essential to assess the environmental impact and sustainability of these materials throughout their lifecycle, including their disposal and recycling options.

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) show great promise for air purification, but practical application is hindered by challenges related to material stability, scalability, and system integration. Future research should prioritize enhancing the durability and lifespan of MOFs in real-world conditions while addressing aggregation and reconfiguration issues. Optimizing synthesis processes to lower costs and improve availability is also crucial. Furthermore, exploring the integration of MOFs with other purification technologies, such as filters or coatings, may yield innovative solutions for better air quality.

Catalytic technologies, particularly photocatalytic oxidation, offer significant potential for air purification but face challenges concerning efficiency, by-product formation, and catalyst longevity. Future investigations should focus on developing new photocatalytic materials with greater activity and stability. Addressing the generation of potentially harmful by-products during the photocatalytic process is vital for ensuring environmental and health safety.

It's important to highlight that the relationship between PM_{2.5} emissions from gasoline vehicles, the induction period of gasoline, and the quantities of olefin and diolefin hydrocarbons in fuel has not been extensively studied. We aim to explore this area in our upcoming research.

The use of fuel additives to mitigate emissions poses challenges related to their effectiveness, environmental impact, and regulatory compliance. Future research should concentrate on developing and testing new additives, including oxygenates, that enhance combustion efficiency while minimizing oxidation and pollutant formation. This approach could potentially increase the induction period of gasoline. Understanding the long-term effects of additives on engine performance and emissions is crucial for their practical use. Improved regulatory frameworks and standardization for evaluating the performance and safety of fuel additives are also needed. Additionally, exploring alternative strategies for emission reduction, such as advanced exhaust treatment technologies and hybrid systems, will be important for addressing the complexities of vehicle emissions and their effects on air quality.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships

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